

Horizon 2020

Research and Innovation Framework Program

CHESS
SET UP

Deliverable 7.5

Project Final Brochure and Video

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06/07/2020	1	Edenway	First version	Pending to add final versions of the brochure and video
28/09/2020	2	Edenway	Added the last versions	Finished

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1. Introduction

The Communication and Dissemination Plan of CHESSE SETUP Project (D7.1 Detailed Communication and Dissemination Plan) presented various strategic objectives (Figure 1). Among others, raise awareness among the building sector about CHESSE SETUP's mission and the benefits, develop a set of communication tools, activities and channels to reach the targeted audience and publication of results and tools developed in the project.

*Figure 1. Strategic objectives of communication and dissemination
(Source: D7.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan, CHESSE SETUP Project)*

Since the beginning of the project, public communication materials have been considered essential for CHESSE SETUP and publicly available contents have been packed into the following communication formats and publications:

- **Graphical materials**
 - **Project Leaflet**
 - **Project Final Brochure**
- **Project Final Video**

Mention that **press releases, newsletters, social media campaigns, website, networking and events materials such as presentations** have been also publicly published online and described in their own final Deliverables of Work Package 7 – Communication and Dissemination.

2. Graphical materials

The leaflet and final brochure have been conceived as fast tools to give an overlook of the system implemented, and the potential scope of its achievements.

Project Initial Leaflet

In September 2016, during the first phase of the project, a leaflet was edited, printed and released to support CHESSETUP's presence in events, conferences, or for one-to-one exchanges.

The leaflet was sent to every CHESSETUP member so they could easily distribute them to potential stakeholders. Besides, a dematerialized/digital version has been in the project website available to download. The leaflet samples were printed on request, and according to the upcoming events. To avoid any paper waste, and in order to the level of dematerialization of the communication activities, there was not any quota or impressions' objective.

It was designed to provide CHESSETUP's first stakeholders with an easy and concise overview of the project and system (Deliverable 7.3). In particular, the leaflet presented the following aspects:

- **What?** Description of the project.
- **What for?** Main objectives and targets of the project.
- **How?** Brief explanation about the system functioning.
- **Why?** A specific focus on the reasons and expected project impacts.
- **Who?** The consortium (partners' logos) and the 3 pilot locations.
- **Website and social media channels** (at that moment only Twitter because LinkedIn was created later) and **EU-funding**.

CHESSETUP's leaflet was developed by Edenway SL, as the coordinator of Work Package 6, and validated by the project leader Barcelona Ecologia.

Figure 2. CHESSETUP's leaflet (Source: Own elaboration)

Link [to the Leaflet digital version](#) uploaded in the CHESSETUP website, available to

download.

Project Final Brochure

At the last phase of the project, in July 2020, the final brochure was designed, edited, and finally released in September 2020 to present the final results of CHESSETUP. It is available in English, Spanish and French languages with the aim to cover a wider audience.

The brochure was sent to every CHESSETUP member so they could easily distribute them to potential stakeholders and a dematerialized version was uploaded in the project website available to download. Furthermore, the brochure has been disseminated through other CHESSETUP communication channels such as social media (Twitter and LinkedIn pages), last newsletter, press release and divulgation article which were externally published in BUILD UP – The European Portal for Energy Efficiency in Buildings and the 7th volume of the Project Repository Journal (PRj, edma, European Dissemination Media Agency). It was also mentioned in the Final Conference of CHESSETUP in 18th September and sent to all the participants, and will also be used to introduce the system to companies/organizations which are presenting interest in the system implementation (in Deliverable 6.4 an example list of these stakeholders is exposed).

The brochure has not been printed and until now has only been published and disseminated in a digital format, in order to dematerialize and make more sustainable the communication strategy of the project.

It was designed to provide CHESSETUP's stakeholders a complete and more concise overview of the project and system by adding the final results, lessons learned and conclusions at the end of the project. The brochure gives the following information about CHESSETUP:

- **Contextualization and need** of the project
- **Main and specific objectives** of the project
- The **Consortium** with description of the multidisciplinary team
- **System's operation**
- The **3 pilot cases** description and results
- **Conclusions, outcomes**

CHESSETUP's leaflet was developed by Edenway SL, as the coordinator of Work Package 6, and validated by the project coordinator Barcelona Ecologia.

Figure 3. Sample of CHESSE SETUP's brochure. (Source: Own elaboration)

Link to the Final Brochure digital version uploaded in the CHESSE SETUP website: available to view and download in [English](#), [Spanish](#) and [French](#).

3. Video production

In order to disseminate the project, its results and CHESSE SETUP system, the Consortium has also included the production of a final video into the Communication and Dissemination Strategy of the project.

Project Final Video

A narrative web video in English has been produced to present the project and its results in an easy-to-understand way, based on animations and infographics and addressing potential stakeholders at large (well-fitted for non-technical stakeholders, but also for technical ones).

As stated in the Grant Agreement, the video has been uploaded on the website front-page in order to attract visitors and provide a graphical “frame” of it. The video was premiered in the Final Conference of CHESSE SETUP and also distributed in the same channels used for the Final Brochure dissemination (social media - Twitter and LinkedIn pages-, last newsletter and press release which where externally released in BUILD UP – The European Portal for Energy Efficiency in Buildings). Due to the action of streaming the Final Conference via YouTube, CHESSE SETUP also created a channel in this video platform and it has uploaded there, adding a new channel for disseminating the final results and exploit the system.

The 5 minutes video followed the same content structure of the brochure, presenting in a visual way the following information about CHESSE SETUP:

- **Contextualization and need** of the project
- **Main and specific objectives** of the project
- The **Consortium** with description of the multidisciplinary team
- **System's** operation and elements
- The **3 pilot cases** description and results with interventions by representatives of the 3 organizations coordinating the pilots (LaVola, Ajuntament de Sant Cugat and Electric Corby)
- **Conclusions** of the project and the system.

Figure 4. Final Video published in CHESSE SETUP website

You can watch the video directly in the [Home Page of CHESSE SETUP website here](#).

Or in our [YouTube channel here](#).

4. Conclusions: Impact

Both final brochure and video were released at the last month of the project, in order to provide these last communication materials with the concrete final results of the pilots achieved at the end of summer. A qualitative impact could be stated due to the positive feedback received by the partners, their close ecosystem, the interest of different companies in the system (see more in Deliverable 6.4) and the audience of the Final Conference. However, it is not possible to present a representative quantitative impact due to the short time margin between their planned publication at the end of the project and the submission of this deliverable.

From the release in early-mid September until the submission date of this deliverable the impact is presented below, following the set of general Key Performance Indicators presented in the plan of Deliverable 7.1 (Figure 5).

TYPE OF CHANNEL	Echo	General
Social media/Newsletter	N° subscribers/followers Popularity of the messages Audience of the subscribers Initial meeting w/ stakeholders	Publications' frequency N° types of newsletters (adaptation to the public)
Website	N° direct contacts from form Questions asked N° documentation downloads N° views of the promotional video	Uploads' frequency FAQ's edition (Y/N) Infography edition Video (Y/N)
Clustering Activities	N° people attending presentation N° people stopping at the stand Initial meeting w/ stakeholders Relevant informations gathered N° people attending the kick off meeting N° people attending the final conference	N° abstracts sent N° attending event Time spent on strategic watch Time spent on workshops' organisation
Local events	N° people attending People's involvement	N° meetings organised Positive evaluation
One-to-one communication	N° people concerned N° of new contacts Relevant informations gathered	Average time spent answering Time spent canvassing potential stakeholders Follow-up of this exchanges
Press	N° edited N° publications in journals/magazines/portals N° publications in generalist journals/magazines/portal Audience of the publications	Abstracts, articles sent Contact with journalists/editors N° Press Releases

Figure 5. KPIs for type of channel for communicate and disseminate activities during CHESS SETUP Project (Source: D7.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan, CHESS SETUP Project)

In the case of the **final brochure** these KPIs are adapted as follows due to availability

of data until this moment:

- **Type of channel:** for communicate and disseminate the project.

Website, Social Media, Newsletter, Clustering Activities, Press

- **General:** referring to the **input** indicators.

1. Number of channels where the final brochure was disseminated

6 channels:

- CHESSE SETUP Website and partners website (e.g. BcnEcologia)
- Twitter and LinkedIn
- 8th Newsletter of CHESSE SETUP
- Final Conference of CHESSE SETUP
- Press Release 4 (Build Up) and Divulgarion Article (Project Repository Journal, EDMA – European Dissemination Media Agency).
- Direct mailing campaign to stakeholders'

- **Echo:** referring to the **output** indicators which give the impact of the activity.

2. Number of views in the last Newsletter (published 28/08/2020) where the final brochure was added

40 views (Retrieved: 28/08/2020)

3. Number of direct audience (registrants) of the Final Conference that have received the final brochure

76 people

4. Number of type/s of audience or stakeholders/target groups reached via the final journals/magazines/portal revues

6 stakeholders/target groups specified in D7.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan: building sector, energy sector, urban planners, installation providers, academia and R&D, European ecosystem and civil society

On the other hand, for the **video**, these KPIs are adapted as follows due to availability of data until this moment:

- **Type of channel:** for communicate and disseminate the project.

Website, Social Media/Newsletter, Clustering Activities, Press

- **General:** referring to the **input** indicators.

5. Number of channels where the final video was disseminated

6 channels:

- CHESSE SETUP Website and partners website (e.g. BcnEcologia)
- Twitter and LinkedIn
- 8th Newsletter of CHESSE SETUP
- Final Conference of CHESSE SETUP
- Divulcation Article (Project Repository Journal, EDMA – European Dissemination Media Agency).
- Direct mailing campaign to stakeholders'

- **Echo:** referring to the **output** indicators which give the impact of the activity.

6. Number of audience (participants) of the Final Conference that have watched *in situ* and received the link to the final video

57 people in the virtual meeting

76 people registered who received the link with the final materials, including the video

7. Number of type/s of audience or stakeholders/target groups reached via the final journals/magazines/portals

6 stakeholders/target groups specified in D7.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan: building sector, energy sector, urban planners, installation providers, academia and R&D, European ecosystem and civil society

Annex. Project Final Brochure

- 1. English**
- 2. Spanish**
- 3. French**

CHESS
SET UP

CHESS SETUP

Combined HEat SyStem by using Solar Energy and heat pUmPs

edenway

Wansdrone

VEOLIA

Electric Corby
Switched on thinking

Ulster University

WATIA
Innovative Energy Solutions

Anthesis Lavola

Ajustement de Saint-Cugat

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement n.680556

CHESS SETUP PROJECT

CHESS SETUP is a H2020 EU Research and Innovation Programme funded project, which has designed a technology solution aiming to increase the energy efficiency, self-sufficiency and renewables implementation in **buildings**.

Why?

Start date:

June 2016

End date:

September 2020

EU BUILDING SECTOR

The European Union has set ambitious targets in order to reduce green house gases (GHG) emissions and the building sector has to do its part, with new buildings required to be “nearly zero-energy buildings” (NZEB). By using energy more efficiently and from renewable sources, a reduction on energy bills and reliance on external energy suppliers can be achieved while protecting the environment. Especially, heating and cooling (H&C) demand accounts for a significant proportion of the European total final energy demand (50%) [1].

40%

OF THE ENERGY
CONSUMED IN
THE EU

36%

OF THE CO₂
EMISSIONS IN
THE EU

In EU households, heating and hot water alone account for 79% of total final energy use. Cooling is a fairly small share of the total final energy use, but demand from households and businesses is rising during the summer months. Moreover, most of the thermal energy is produced from fossil fuels (66%) and only 13% comes from renewable energy [1].

THE OBJECTIVES

The main objective of the project is to implement a reliable and efficient system able to supply **heating, cooling and domestic hot water in buildings** mainly from renewable energy sources, including seasonal energy storage, increasing its self-sufficiency and reducing its emissions.

CHESSE SETUP system is technically easy to implement for new build construction projects, but it can also be adapted while retrofitting existing buildings.

Implement a new heating solution based on a trio of technologies on a **seasonal mode**- hybrid photovoltaic-thermal solar panels, a thermal storage system and heat pump

Test and monitor the system in 3 different geographical situations and types of building, with a proper **software**

Reduce the electricity demand peak, relying on the system inertia, and allow renewable energies' connection to grid

Improve the initial system, and make it **compatible** with renewable energies' back up sources

Develop business models from the use cases in order to **industrialize** CHESSE SETUP's achievements

Reach a reduction **greater than 15%** of investment costs compared to other highly efficient heating systems

THE CONSORTIUM

University committed to the economic, social and cultural development (**NORTHERN IRELAND**)

Urban Ecology Agency of Barcelona, rethinking the metropolis from a sustainable point of view (**SPAIN**)

Company specialized in energy efficiency to improve all kinds of facilities (**SPAIN**)

City council of Sant Cugat del Vallès with a clear sustainable growth strategy (**SPAIN**)

Consulting firm dedicated to economic, social and environmental sustainability (**SPAIN**)

Energy and Environmental Service Company (**SPAIN**)

A Community Interest Company establishing Corby as demonstrator for future sustainable living, working and transportation (**UNITED KINGDOM**)

Architecture studio establishing the building concept Emporium (**THE NETHERLANDS**)

Spin-off from the European Project Center of the Technical University of Dresden (**GERMANY**)

Paris and Barcelona consulting firm specialized in the integral management of innovative and sustainable projects (**FRANCE, SPAIN**)

THE SYSTEM

THE SYSTEM CAN BE COMBINED WITH OTHER RENEWABLE SOURCES AND CAN BE ADAPTED TO ANY LOCAL CLIMATE AND SITE CHARACTERISTICS

Seasonal thermal storage: stores the heat collected by the panels increasing the temperature of the medium, that can be liquid or solid.

Heat pump: supplies heating and DHW demands of the building, recovering the heat stored in the seasonal storages at high efficiencies.

SUMMER

There is **high solar radiation** and **low heat demand**. The share of the collected energy which is not used is transferred to the seasonal storage tank to be stored.

WINTER

The **demand for heat increases**, and **solar radiation is lower**. Therefore, the heat pump transfers the heat stored during the summer with very low electricity consumption, to satisfy the energy demand of the building.

THE PILOT CASES

The system was installed in **three different pilot sites**, sizing the elements according to the buildings' characteristics such as the solar irradiation, energy demands, and available surface for the installation of panels and the thermal storage tank. **The positive effects of the system were showed in all pilot cases.**

SANT CUGAT SPAIN

BUILDING SPORT CENTER
CLIMATE MEDITERRANEAN
PROJECT LARGE STORAGE TANK

The system installed in this sport center, with more than 6.000 users, is used for the climatization of the swimming pool. A large storage tank (100 m³), a heat pump and 160 PVT solar panels were placed. The system is already generating both thermal and electric energy, storing the thermal energy in the tank and heating the swimming pool using the high efficiency heat pump.

240 MWh/yr
7%

ENERGY SAVED
(Natural Gas and Electricity)

61,1 tCO₂/yr
10%

CO₂ emissions SAVED

THE PILOT CASES

CORBY UK

BUILDING 26 ECOHOMES CLIMATE OCEANIC PROJECT HEAT STORAGE SYSTEM

4,6 MWh/yr
46%

ENERGY SAVED
per home
(100% Natural Gas)

1,8 tCO₂/yr
85%

CO₂ emissions
SAVED per home

The system takes generated heat energy and stores this underground. The stored heat is then withdrawn from the Earth Energy bank for use within the building via a heat pump, which increases the temperature to a level that can be used for space heating and domestic hot water. The heat pump was integrated in the existing control system.

MANLLEU SPAIN

BUILDING OFFICE BUILDING CLIMATE MEDITERRANEAN PROJECT SHORT TERM STORAGE

65,4 MWh/yr
47%

ENERGY SAVED
(100% Natural Gas)

18,9 tCO₂/yr
65%

CO₂ emissions
SAVED

The system in LaVola company headquarters consists on a PV installation, a heat pump, meters and control-hydraulic installation. This pilot helps demonstrating that the system can also be suitable in existing buildings with limited space for the storage tank.

CONCLUSIONS

CHESSE SETUP can allow significant energy savings for buildings: the energy produced on-site will be consumed on site or reverted to the power grid if necessary.

CHESSE SETUP makes the energetic needs of the buildings residual, thanks to the use of renewable energy collected and transformed on site. This means a decrease in GHG emissions and an improvement in energy efficiency, aligned with the EU Goals.

CHESSE SETUP is an economically exploitable model. Being a centralised system it also reduces maintenance costs and energy losses. Both the pilot sites implementation have shown that is a suitable technical and environmental solution, as well as economically viable. Strategic alliances with manufacturers, suppliers, engineering companies and interested parties could open the range of opportunities to replicate the CHESSE SETUP model, reducing costs and scaling the implementation of the system.

CHESSE SETUP brings key solutions for our future: a self-consumption system that could drive us towards NZEB, energy independence, a higher productivity of the grids and a low-carbon society.

[@chesssetup](https://twitter.com/chesssetup)

[chess-setup](https://www.linkedin.com/company/chess-setup)

www.chess-setup.net

CHESS
SET UP

CHESS SETUP

Combined **HEat SyStem** by using **Solar Energy** and **heaT pUmPs**

Sistema de calor combinado mediante el uso de energía solar y bombas de calor

edenway

VEOLIA

WATIA
Innovative Energy Solutions

Anthesis Lavola

Este proyecto ha recibido fondos del programa H2020 de Investigación e Innovación de la Unión Europea bajo el acuerdo de subvención n.680556

EL PROYECTO CHESS SETUP

CHESS SETUP es un proyecto financiado por el programa europeo H2020 de Investigación e Innovación, que ha diseñado una solución tecnológica para aumentar la eficiencia energética, autosuficiencia e implementación de renovables en edificios.

¿Por qué?

Fecha de inicio:

Junio 2016

Fecha de finalización:

Septiembre 2020

SECTOR EUROPEO DE LA EDIFICACIÓN

La Unión Europea (UE) ha marcado objetivos ambiciosos para reducir las emisiones de gases de efecto invernadero (GEI). El sector de la construcción tiene que hacer su parte, con todos los edificios de nueva construcción siendo "edificios de consumo casi nulo" (nZEB). Usando energía de fuentes renovables y de manera más eficiente, se puede alcanzar una reducción de las facturas y de la dependencia de fuentes de energía externa, a la vez que se protege el medioambiente. En concreto, la demanda de calefacción y refrigeración representa una parte significativa de la energía total consumida en Europa (50%) [1].

40% DE LA ENERGÍA CONSUMIDA EN LA UE

36% DE LAS EMISIONES DE CO₂ DE LA UE

Solo la calefacción y el agua caliente sanitaria (ACS) representan un 79% de la energía total consumida en las viviendas europeas. Por otro lado, la refrigeración es solo una pequeña parte de ese total, pero el consumo en casas y negocios aumenta durante el verano. Además, la mayoría de la energía térmica se produce a partir de combustibles fósiles (66%), solo el 13% proviene de fuentes renovables [1].

LOS OBJETIVOS

El principal objetivo del proyecto es implementar un sistema eficiente y seguro capaz de proveer **calefacción, refrigeración y agua caliente sanitaria en edificios**, mayoritariamente procedente de fuentes renovables. El sistema incluye un depósito de almacenamiento estacional que incrementa la autosuficiencia del edificio y reduce las emisiones contaminantes.

CHESSE SETUP es técnicamente fácil de implementar en edificios de nueva construcción pero también se adapta a edificios existentes.

Implementar una solución de calefacción basada en un trío de tecnologías con un **sistema estacional**, paneles híbridos fotovoltaicos-térmicos, almacenamiento térmico y bomba de calor

Mejorar el sistema inicial y hacerlo **compatible** con energías renovables

Probar y monitorear el sistema en 3 ubicaciones diferentes con 3 tipos de edificios diferentes, con la ayuda de un **software**

Desarrollar modelos de negocio para poder **industrializar** los logros de CHESSE SETUP

Reducir el pico de consumo de electricidad, apoyándose en la inercia del sistema y permitiendo la conexión de energías renovables a la red

Alcanzar una **reducción mayor del 15% del coste de inversión inicial** comparado con otros sistemas de calefacción altamente eficientes

EL CONSORCIO

Universidad comprometida con el desarrollo económico, social y cultural (IRLANDA DEL NORTE)

Una compañía con interés por la comunidad, que pone Corby como muestra para una vida, trabajo y movilidad sostenibles (REINO UNIDO)

Agencia de Ecología Urbana de Barcelona, repensado la metrópoli desde un punto de vista sostenible (ESPAÑA)

Empresa especializada en eficiencia energética para mejorar todo tipo de instalaciones (ESPAÑA)

Estudio de arquitectura estableciendo el concepto de edificio Emporium (HOLANDA)

Spin-off del Centro de Proyectos Europeos de la Universidad Técnica de Dresden (ALEMANIA)

Ayuntamiento de Sant Cugat del Vallès con estrategia de crecimiento sostenible para la ciudad (ESPAÑA)

Consultoría dedicada a la sostenibilidad económica, social y medioambiental (ESPAÑA)

Empresa de servicios energéticos y medio ambientales (ESPAÑA)

Consultoría en París y Barcelona especializada en proyectos de innovación y sostenibilidad (FRANCIA, ESPAÑA)

EL SISTEMA

*EL SISTEMA PUEDE SER COMBINADO CON OTRAS FUENTES RENOVABLES
ADAPTÁNDOSE A CUALQUIER CLIMA LOCAL Y CARACTERÍSTICAS DE EMPLAZAMIENTO*

Almacenamiento térmico estacional: almacena el calor recogido por los paneles solares incrementando la temperatura del medio, pudiendo ser sólido o líquido.

Bomba de calor: proporciona calor y ACS al edificio, recuperando la energía almacenada en el acumulador de manera altamente eficiente.

CALOR

ELECTRICIDAD

VERANO

En verano hay una **radiación solar alta** y un **demanda de calor baja**. La parte de energía recogida que no se usa es transferida al depósito de almacenamiento térmico estacional.

INVIERNO

En invierno la **demanda de calor aumenta** y la **radiación solar es más baja**. Por lo tanto, la bomba de calor transfiere el calor almacenado durante el verano con un consumo de electricidad muy bajo para satisfacer la demanda energética del edificio.

LOS PILOTOS

El sistema se instaló en **3 sitios piloto**, dimensionando los elementos acorde con las características de los edificios, como la radiación solar disponible, la demanda energética y la superficie para la instalación de los paneles y el depósito de almacenamiento. **Los efectos positivos del sistema se pudieron ver en todos los pilotos.**

SANT CUGAT
ESPAÑA

EDIFICIO CENTRO DEPORTIVO
CLIMA MEDITERRÁNEO
PROYECTO GRAN DEPÓSITO DE
ALMACENAMIENTO

El sistema instalado en este centro deportivo, con más de 6.000 usuarios, se usa para la climatización de la piscina. Se instaló un acumulador (100 m³), una bomba de calor y 160 paneles solares híbridos. El sistema está ya generando tanto energía térmica como electricidad, almacenando la energía térmica en el depósito y calentando la piscina a través de una bomba de calor de alta eficiencia.

240 MWh/año
7%

**ENERGÍA
AHORRADA**
(Gas natural y electricidad)

61,1 tCO₂/año
10%

**Emisiones CO₂
AHORRADAS**

LOS PILOTOS

CORBY UK

EDIFICIO 26 ECOCASAS CLIMA OCEÁNICO PROYECTO SISTEMA DE ALMACENAMIENTO DE CALOR

4,6 MWh/año

46%

ENERGÍA
AHORRADA por casa

(100% Gas Natural)

1,8 tCO₂/yr

85%

Emisiones CO₂
AHORRADAS
por casa

El sistema almacena la energía térmica generada en el depósito bajo tierra. Ésta después se extrae del depósito (*Earth Energy Bank*) mediante una bomba de calor que también aumenta la temperatura para que pueda ser usada para calefacción y ACS. La bomba de calor fue integrada en el sistema de control ya existente.

MANLLEU ESPAÑA

EDIFICIO OFICINAS CLIMA MEDITERRÁNEO PROYECTO ALMACENAMIENTO A CORTO PLAZO

65,4 MWh/yr

47%

ENERGÍA
AHORRADA
(100% Gas Natural)

18,9 tCO₂/yr

65%

Emisiones CO₂
AHORRADAS

En las oficinas de LaVola, el sistema consta de una instalación fotovoltaica, una bomba de calor, contadores e instalación de control-hidráulico. Este piloto ayuda a demostrar que el sistema también puede ser adecuado en edificios existentes con espacio limitado para el depósito de almacenamiento.

CONCLUSIONES

CHESSE SETUP puede generar ahorros de energía significativos para los edificios: la energía eléctrica producida en el sitio se consumirá en el sitio o, se inyectará a la red, si es necesario.

CHESSE SETUP hace residuales las necesidades energéticas de los edificios, gracias al uso de energías renovables recogidas y transformadas *in situ*. Esto implica una disminución de las emisiones de gases de efecto invernadero y una mejora de la eficiencia energética, alineada con los Objetivos de la Unión Europea.

CHESSE SETUP es un modelo económicamente explotable. Al ser un sistema centralizado, también reduce los costes de mantenimiento y las pérdidas de energía. La implementación de los pilotos ha demostrado que es una solución técnica y ambiental adecuada, así como económicamente viable. Las alianzas estratégicas con fabricantes, proveedores, empresas de ingeniería y partes interesadas podrían abrir el abanico de oportunidades para replicar el modelo CHESSE SETUP, reduciendo costes y escalando la implementación del sistema.

CHESSE SETUP aporta soluciones clave para nuestro futuro: un sistema de autoconsumo que podría impulsarnos hacia los Edificios de Consumo Casi Nulo, la independencia energética, una mayor productividad de las redes y una sociedad baja en carbono.

[@chesssetup](https://twitter.com/chesssetup)

[chess-setup](https://www.chess-setup.net)

www.chess-setup.net

CHESS
SET UP

CHESS SETUP

Combined **HEat SyStem** by using **Solar Energy** and **heaT pUmPs**

Système de chauffage combiné utilisant l'énergie solaire et les pompes à chaleur

edenway

Wansdronk

VEOLIA

Electric
Corby
Switched on thinking

WATIA
Innovative Energy Solutions

Anthesis Lavola

Ajuntament
de Sant Cugat

Ce projet a reçu un financement du programme de recherche et d'innovation Horizon 2020 de l'Union européenne au titre de la convention de subvention n° 680556

LE PROJET CHESS SETUP

CHESS SETUP est un projet co-financé par le programme de recherche et d'innovation H2020 de l'UE, qui a conçu une solution technologique visant à améliorer l'efficacité énergétique, l'autosuffisance et la mise en œuvre des énergies renouvelables dans les **bâtiments**.

Pourquoi?

Date de démarrage:

Juin 2016

Date de fin:

Septembre 2020

LE SECTEUR DU BÂTIMENT EN EUROPE

L'Union européenne s'est fixée des objectifs ambitieux afin de réduire les émissions de gaz à effet de serre (GES) et le secteur du bâtiment doit y prendre part, avec de nouveaux bâtiments dont la consommation d'énergie doit être quasi nulle (NZEB). En utilisant de l'énergie de manière plus efficace et venant de source renouvelable, une réduction des factures d'énergie et de la dépendance de fournisseurs d'énergie externes peuvent être atteints tout en protégeant l'environnement. En particulier, les systèmes de chauffage et de climatisation représentent une part importante de la demande énergétique totale européenne (50%) ^[1].

40%

DE LA
CONSOMMATION
ÉNERGÉTIQUE
EUROPÉENNE

36%

DES ÉMISSIONS DE
CO₂ EUROPÉENNES

Dans les foyers de l'UE, le chauffage et l'eau chaude représentent à eux seuls 79% de la consommation totale d'énergie. Le refroidissement représente une part relativement faible de la consommation totale d'énergie, mais la demande des ménages et des entreprises augmente en été. De plus, la majeure partie de l'énergie thermique est produite à partir de combustibles fossiles (66%) et seulement 13% provient d'énergies renouvelables ^[1].

LES OBJECTIFS

L'objectif principal du projet est de mettre en œuvre un système fiable et efficace capable de fournir **du chauffage, de la climatisation et de l'eau chaude sanitaire dans les bâtiments**, principalement à partir de sources d'énergies renouvelables, en incluant le stockage saisonnier de l'énergie, en augmentant son autosuffisance et en réduisant ses émissions.

Le **système CHESSE SETUP** est techniquement facile à mettre en œuvre pour les nouveaux projets de construction, mais il peut également être adapté lors de la réhabilitation de bâtiments existants.

Mettre en œuvre une nouvelle solution de chauffage basée sur un trio de technologies sur un **mode saisonnier** -
- panneaux solaires thermiques,
- un système de stockage thermique et une pompe à chaleur

Améliorer le système initial et le rendre **compatible** avec les sources d'énergies renouvelables utilisées en backup

Tester et suivre le système dans 3 zones géographiques et types de bâtiments différents, grâce à un **logiciel** approprié

Développer des modèles économiques à partir des pilotes afin d'**industrialiser** les réalisations de CHESSE SETUP

Réduire le pic de demande d'électricité, en s'appuyant sur l'inertie du système, et permettre la connexion des énergies renouvelables au réseau

Atteindre une réduction de **plus de 15% des coûts d'investissement** par rapport à d'autres systèmes de chauffage très efficaces

LE CONSORTIUM

Université engagée dans le développement économique, social et culturel (IRLANDE DU NORD)

Une société d'intérêt communautaire établissant la ville de Corby comme démonstrateur pour les modes de vie, de travail et de transport durables du futur (ROYAUME-UNI)

Agence d'écologie urbaine de Barcelone, repenser la métropole d'un point de vue durable (ESPAGNE)

Entreprise spécialisée dans l'efficacité énergétique pour améliorer tout type d'installations (ESPAGNE)

Studio d'architecture à l'origine du concept de bâtiment *Emporium* (PAYS-BAS)

Spin-off du Centre de projets européens de l'Université technique de Dresde (ALLEMAGNE)

Mairie de Sant Cugat del Vallès avec une stratégie claire de croissance durable (ESPAGNE)

Cabinet de conseil spécialisé dans le domaine du développement durable (ESPAGNE)

Entreprise de services énergétiques et environnementaux (ESPAGNE)

Cabinet de conseil spécialisé dans la gestion intégrale de projets innovants et durables (FRANCE, ESPAGNE)

LE SYSTÈME

LE SYSTÈME PEUT ÊTRE COMBINÉ AVEC D'AUTRES SOURCES D'ÉNERGIES RENOUVELABLES ET PEUT ÊTRE ADAPTÉ À TOUT TYPE DE CLIMAT ET CARACTÉRISTIQUES SPECIFIQUES D'UN SITE

Stockage thermique saisonnier: accumule la chaleur collectée par les panneaux augmentant la température du milieu, qu'il soit liquide ou solide.

Pompe à chaleur: fournit les besoins de chauffage et d'ECS du bâtiment, récupérant la chaleur stockée dans les réserves saisonnières très performantes.

ÉTÉ

Le rayonnement solaire est élevé et le besoin de chaleur est faible. La part de l'énergie collectée qui n'est pas utilisée est transférée à la réserve de stockage saisonnière.

HIVER

La demande de chaleur augmente et le rayonnement solaire est plus faible. Par conséquent, la pompe à chaleur transfère la chaleur emmagasinée pendant l'été avec une consommation électrique très faible, pour satisfaire la demande énergétique du bâtiment.

LES PROJETS PILOTES

Le système a été installé sur **trois sites pilotes** différents, dimensionnant les éléments en fonction des caractéristiques des bâtiments telles que l'irradiation solaire, les besoins énergétiques et la surface disponible pour l'installation des panneaux et du réservoir de stockage thermique. **Les effets positifs du système ont été mis en évidence dans tous les cas pilotes.**

SANT CUGAT ESPAGNE

BÂTIMENT COMPLEXE SPORTIF
CLIMAT MÉDITERRANÉEN
PROJET GRAND RÉSERVOIR DE STOCKAGE

Le système installé dans ce centre sportif, qui compte avec plus de 6.000 utilisateurs, est utilisé pour la climatisation de la piscine. Un réservoir de stockage (100 m³), une pompe à chaleur et 160 panneaux solaires hybrides ont été installés. Le système produit déjà de l'énergie thermique et électrique, stocke l'énergie thermique dans le réservoir et chauffe la piscine avec une pompe à haut rendement.

240 MWh/an
7%

**ÉCONOMIE
D'ÉNERGIE**
(Gas Naturel et Electricité)

61,1 tCO₂/an
10%

**RÉDUCTION
d'émissions
de CO₂**

LES PROJETS PILOTES

CORBY UK

BÂTIMENT 26 ECOLOGEMENTS CLIMAT OCÉANIQUE PROJET SYSTÈME DE STOCKAGE DE CHALEUR

4,6 MWh/an

46%

ÉCONOMIE
D'ÉNERGIE par
logement

(100% Gas Naturel)

1,8 tCO₂/an

85%

RÉDUCTION
d'émissions de
CO₂ par logement

Le système récupère l'énergie thermique produite et la stocke dans le sous-sol. La chaleur stockée est ensuite extraite de la Banque d'Énergie Terrestre (EEB) pour être utilisée dans le bâtiment via une pompe à chaleur, qui augmente la température à un niveau qui peut être utilisé pour le chauffage et l'eau chaude. La pompe à chaleur a été intégrée dans le système de contrôle existant.

MANILLEU ESPAGNE

BÂTIMENT BUREAUX CLIMAT MÉDITERRANÉEN PROJET STOCKAGE À COURT TERME

65,4 MWh/an

47%

ÉCONOMIE
D'ÉNERGIE

(100% Gas Naturel)

18,9 tCO₂/an

65%

RÉDUCTION
d'émissions de
CO₂

Le système mis en place au siège de l'entreprise Lavola est composé d'une installation photovoltaïque, d'une pompe à chaleur, de compteurs et d'une installation de régulation hydraulique. Ce pilote permet de démontrer que le système peut également être adapté dans des bâtiments existants et ayant un espace limité pour le réservoir de stockage.

CONCLUSIONS

CHESSE SETUP peut permettre d'importantes économies d'énergie pour les bâtiments: l'énergie produite sur place sera consommée sur site ou réinjectée sur le réseau électrique si nécessaire.

CHESSE SETUP rend résiduels les besoins énergétiques des bâtiments, grâce à l'utilisation d'énergies renouvelables collectées et transformées sur place. Cela permet une diminution des émissions de GES et une amélioration de l'efficacité énergétique, conformément aux objectifs de l'UE.

CHESSE SETUP est un modèle économiquement exploitable. En tant que système centralisé, il réduit également les coûts de maintenance et les pertes d'énergie. La mise en œuvre des deux sites pilotes a montré qu'il s'agissait d'une solution technique et environnementale adaptée et économiquement viable. Des alliances stratégiques avec des fabricants, des fournisseurs, des sociétés d'ingénierie et des parties prenantes devraient permettre de multiplier les opportunités pour reproduire le modèle CHESSE SETUP, en réduisant ainsi les coûts et en permettant la réplication du système.

CHESSE SETUP apporte des solutions clés pour notre avenir: un système d'autoconsommation qui pourrait nous conduire vers une consommation énergétique quasi-nulle, l'indépendance énergétique, une plus grande productivité des réseaux et une société à faible émission de carbone.

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